

Some Newer Cyanoethylated Alkyl and Aryl Substituted Cyanoacetamides as Insecticides. Part III.

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Alkyl and aryl substituted cyanoacetamides were condensed. The products thus obtained, were further cyanoethylated. These newer compounds were evaluated for their insecticidal property for obtaining a better knowledge of their physiological significance.

HASS *et al*¹ have tested several diarylnitroalkane nitriles for insecticidal property and some of them proved good insecticides. Misra and Asthana² prepared cyanoethylated product of sulphones and sulphonamides. They showed considerable toxicity to house fly.

With a view to study other cyanoethylated compounds as insecticides, alkyl and aryl substituted cyanoacetamides were synthesized by condensing aliphatic and aromatic amines (methylamine, ethylamine, propylamine, isopropylamine, butylamine, *o*-toluidine, benzylamine, α -naphthylamine and β -naphthylamine), with ethylcyanoacetate according to the method of Naik and Bhat³, Naik and Shah⁴ and Bakes *et al*⁵.

The substituted cyanoacetamides thus prepared were cyanoethylated with acrylonitrile in dioxan solvent using benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide as catalyst at room temperature.

In all the compounds the active methylene group reacts with two moles of acrylonitrile to give a dicyano-ethylation product. The infrared spectra of α -cyano, α , α -bis- (β -cyanoethyl) (R) amides were recorded and they show-C=N stretching band at 2250~2210 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Cyanoethylation of Cyanoacet-methylamide : Acrylonitrile (1 mol) was added dropwise to a reaction mixture of cyanoacet-methylamide (0.5 mol) in dioxan solvent and benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide as catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3-4 hr. and then neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid. The solvent was distilled off at reduced pressure and the residual mass was dried over vacuum which solidified on standing. It was recrystallized from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 90°. Similarly the cyanoacet-(ethylamide, propylamide and butylamide) were cyanoethylated. They are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1— α -CYANO, α , α -BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) (R) AMIDES

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Nitrogen %	
				(Calcd.)	(Found)
1.	Methyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ O	90	27.45	27.50
2.	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	62	25.68	25.62
3.	Propyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	48	24.13	24.20
4.	Isopropyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	86-87	24.13	24.12
5.	Butyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	118	22.76	22.80
6.	<i>o</i> -toluidide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	85	20.00	20.01
7.	Benzyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	84-85	20.00	19.98
8.	α -naphthyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	78	17.72	17.81
9.	β -naphthyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	89	17.72	17.68

In the cyanoethylation of cyanoacet-iso-propylamide the extraction of the final product was carried out with ethylene dichloride and the solvent was removed by vacuum distillation.

Cyanoethylation of cyanoacet-(*o*-toluidide, benzylamide, and α & β -naphthylamide) was carried out in the same above manner except, the recovery of cyanoethylated compound after neutralisation of the reaction mixture with dilute hydrochloric acid, was done by pouring the solution in ice water to obtain the solid product. It was then recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 2—INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF REFERENCE COMPOUNDS

S.no.	Name of compound	Concentration %	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds.
1.	D. D. T.	0.5	305
2.	BHC	0.5	300
3.	Pyrethrum solution	0.5	422

The compounds synthesized were tested for their insecticidal activity on house fly '*Musca domestica*'.

Method of testing insecticidal activity : The biological assay of all compounds described here was carried.

All the compounds were dissolved in acetone. 2% concentration of the samples were made as stock solution. Later, the desired dilutions (0.5%, 1%) were made and applied topically with an 'Agl'a' micrometer syringe keeping the volume constant at 0.001 per fly. The tests were carried against males 3-4 days old. Tests were done in triplicate and such batch contained 20 flies. The control was applied with acetone.

For the sake of comparison the results obtained with DDT, BHC and pyrethrum when applied by the same method are also recorded.

Results and Discussion

In Table 3, the first compound with methyl substituent showed the highest toxicity and as the alkyl chain increases, the insecticidal activity decreases. The order of toxicity is as : methyl > ethyl > propyl > butyl > toluidide.

In Table 4, the derivatives of α, α , bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondi (R) amides, where R is variable, in aliphatic chain from methyl to butyl and aryl are listed. The aliphatic series has shown similar trend of toxicity as in table 3. But, however, when R is a benzyl group, the compound becomes non-toxic.

In Table 5, contrary to other results described in the literature, that chloro derivatives of cyanoethylated compound increases the insecticidal property. It is surprising to note the α -cyano- α -butyl, α - β -cyanoethyl-*p*-chlorophenylanilide was not toxic at all even at the concentration of five percent. Other compounds in this series also showed very little toxicity.

TABLE 3—INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF α -CYANO, α, α BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) (R) AMIDE

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{RNHOC} \quad \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN} \\ \quad \quad \quad \diagdown \quad / \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{C} \\ \quad \quad \quad / \quad \diagdown \\ \text{NC} \quad \quad \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN} \end{array}$$

S.No.	R	Concentration %	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	Methyl	0.5	540
2.	Ethyl	0.5	625
3.	Propyl	0.5	738
4.	Butyl	0.5	820
5.	Toluidide	0.5	910

TABLE 4—INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF α, α , BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) MALONDI (R) AMIDE.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{RNHOC} \quad \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN} \\ \quad \quad \quad \diagdown \quad / \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{C} \\ \quad \quad \quad / \quad \diagdown \\ \text{RNHOC} \quad \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN} \end{array}$$

S.No.	R	Concentration %	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	Methyl	0.5	812
2.	Ethyl	0.5	980
3.	Propyl	0.5	998
4.	Butyl	0.5	1050
5.	Benzyl	0.5	No toxicity

TABLE 5—INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF α -CYANO, α -BUTYL, α -(β -CYANOETHYL) (R) ANILIDE

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{RNHOC} \quad \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN} \\ \quad \quad \quad \diagdown \quad / \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{C} \\ \quad \quad \quad / \quad \diagdown \\ \text{CN} \quad \quad \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array}$$

S.No.	R	Concentration %	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	Phenyl	0.5	1500
2.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	0.5	No toxicity
3.	<i>p</i> -anisole	0.5	3220
4.	<i>p</i> -toluene	0.5	917
5.	<i>p</i> -toluene	0.5	1058

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